

Between the Lines: Leveraging LLMs for Information Extraction of Subsea Data Cable News

Jonas Franken*, Kasimir Romer†, Timon Dörnfeld*, Paula Meissner*, and Christian Reuter*

*Science and Technology for Peace and Security (PEASEC), Technical University of Darmstadt, Darmstadt, Germany

Emails: [lastname]@peasec.tu-darmstadt.de

†Department of Computer Science, Technical University of Darmstadt, Darmstadt, Germany

Abstract—This paper investigates the potential of Large Language Models (LLMs) in automating the extraction and analysis of Subsea Data Cables (SDCs)-related information from unstructured media sources. A comprehensive LLM-based information extraction module was developed and integrated into an existing SDC database. By systematically comparing different LLMs, including GPT-4o, Gemini 1.5 Flash, Claude 3.5 Sonnet, and Llama 3.1, this work identifies optimal model configurations for SDC news processing, considering accuracy, hallucination rate, and processing speed. The system implements Claude 3.5 Sonnet and GPT4-o as primary models, incorporating domain-specific prompt engineering and robust output validation mechanisms. Performance evaluation demonstrates substantial improvements over rule-based methods. While excelling at natural language understanding tasks, the system revealed limitations in extracting more specific technical details such as construction costs and capacity measurements. The implementation provides a modular, adaptable framework for automated information extraction in specialised technical domains. The results demonstrate that LLMs, when properly implemented with structured prompts and validation mechanisms, can significantly enhance the automated monitoring and analysis of SDC-related events.

I. INTRODUCTION

Forming the physical backbone of intercontinental network traffic, Subsea Data Cables (SDCs) are among the most critical infrastructures today [1]. Despite their importance, SDCs tend to be a niche subject with limited presence in the public discourse. This may, in part, be explained with what Bueger and Liebetau [2] call “triple invisibility” of the subsea cable network: namely as infrastructure, as being underground, and as being under the sea. However, the security of SDCs, especially in the Baltic Sea, has recently drawn media attention [3]. Multiple faults of seabed infrastructures caused by anchor drags between October 2023 and February 2025 have been increasingly reported by the news media. Still, media coverage on SDCs in general is sporadic at best, often relegated to specialised industry forums, private online groups, or smaller-scale, regularly updated publications like the *Almanac* by Clark and Humera [4] or *SubCableNews* [5].

This dispersed information landscape creates a significant gap in structured, up-to-date, and machine-readable data, making it difficult to fully assess parallel impacts on the SDC network. To overcome this, the authors propose investigating the usefulness and performance of LLMs in extracting and analysing information from various fragmented news sources regarding SDC. The primary objective is to develop a data pro-

cessing pipeline that collects and analyses news from various sources, suggesting updates to an existing SDC database [6]. This system is specifically designed to monitor SDC news but has a generalised architecture to facilitate easy adaptation for other subjects with minimal effort. Building on previous work of the authors [6], this paper has implemented an LLM-based information extractor that can be integrated into the current pipeline. The research will be guided by the research question (RQ): **How can Large Language Models be applied to extract and process news data on SDCs?**

To address this research question, the work proceeds with an overview of related works (II) in the field of Information Extraction (IE), followed by the methodology (III) that explains the comparative approach taken in the subsequent model analysis (IV). Then, the artifact will be presented (V) and evaluated via post-tests (VI). The work closes with a discussion (VII) and conclusion (VIII).

II. RELATED WORKS

This chapter provides an overview of current research in Information Extraction (IE) with LLMs. While no previous paper has targeted the extraction from SDC-related news, several works focused on other source materials [7].

a) Named Entity Recognition (NER): In the past years, many works have analyzed how LLMs can facilitate NER tasks. Evans, Sadruddin, and D’Souza [8] conducted a survey on how well an LLM can annotate entities in comparison to a human domain expert. Their research found that fine-tuning led to a significant improvement in LLM-performance. Similarly, Bogdanov, Constantin, Bernard, *et al.* [9] used an off-the-shelf LLM to annotate NER data that were then used to train a smaller model in order to save costs. *NuNER* surpassed GPT-3.5 and possibly also GPT-4 after a few training rounds, making it a viable candidate for NER tasks. Likewise, Wang, Sun, Li, *et al.* [10] transformed the NER task into a text generation task, solvable by LLMs. In order to avoid hallucination, they implemented a self-verification stage. Their results showed very good performance, also when training data was scarce. Zhang, Zhao, Gao, *et al.* [11] proposed a framework called *LinkNER* that employed a two-step approach for NER. First, a specialised NER model identified entities in the text and assessed its own confidence in each prediction. Then, any entities the model was uncertain about were passed to a more general LLM for review and refinement. The final

result combined the strengths of both models; the precision of the NER model and the broad knowledge base of the LLM.

b) Relation Extraction (RE): Wan, Cheng, Mao, *et al.* [12] introduced *GPT-RE*, a method to improve how LLMs perform RE tasks, which they have struggled with due to issues such as selecting irrelevant examples and misclassifying missing relationships. *GPT-RE* overcame these challenges by incorporating task-specific entity information and using reasoning logic derived from correct answers. Huguet Cabot and Navigli [13] used the same approach as Zhang, Zhao, Gao, *et al.* [11] and reformulated RE as a text generation problem LLMs can solve. Xu, Zhu, Wang, *et al.* [14] investigated enhancing few-shot RE using GPT-3.5. The study explored two main strategies: In-context learning and data generation. Josifoski, De Cao, Peyrard, *et al.* [15] evaluated their GenIE approach and discovered promising results for RE using a decoder-encoder model.

c) Event Extraction (EE): Of particular interest is Nakshatri *et al.*'s [16] use of LLMs to discover events from news streams. The framework first filtered news articles based on their temporal patterns to focus on periods of high activity and then clustered them to identify potential event candidates, offering great potential to understand the evolution of news narratives and identify key events within large news corpora.

d) Research Gap: Despite the extensive work done in the fields of SDCs, LLMs, and IE, a research gap remains unaddressed in the integration of current events into existing SDC documentation and visualisation approaches. Current maps, such as the Submarine Cable Map [17] or the SDCS Map [6] provide static representations of SDC networks. However, they do not reflect real-time changes or disruptions, such as cable damages, repairs, or new deployments. This paper offers an integrated approach that combines the LLM capabilities in processing natural language with real-time IE tailored to the SDC domain. These advancements can significantly improve global SDC networks' monitoring and analysis but also address the broader issue of IE of topical niches with low training data availability.

III. METHODOLOGY

For the analysis, a variety of well-known industry LLMs were selected for comparison, of which the four LLMs listed in Table I were chosen.

TABLE I: Selection criteria for each LLM

LLM	Selection Criterion
ChatGPT 4o	Market leader for commercial LLMs
Gemini 1.5 Flash	Google's latest model for long texts
Claude 3.5 Sonnet	Documented strength in factual accuracy
Llama 3.1 via HuggingChat	Open-source alternative

To evaluate these models, a dataset was created from SDC-related news articles ($n = 27$) from various outlets. The LLMs were then applied to this dataset to extract relevant data, performing IE tasks, including NER, RE, and EE. The performance evaluation was based on accuracy, depth, hallucination rate, and structural adherence:

a) Accuracy of Extracted Information: Accuracy measures how accurately LLM extracts relevant details from news articles, including names, dates, and specific technical terms. The extracted information was compared against manually verified data to assess how well the model performs.

b) Depth of Extraction: Depth assesses how thoroughly the LLM extracts background information and context from articles, such as technical specifications, historical context, and industry impact. The completeness of the extracted information was rated against a benchmark of manually extracted data.

c) Hallucination Rate: Hallucination refers to the frequency with which the LLM introduces fabricated or incorrect information not present in the original source material. The results were reviewed to identify instances of hallucination.

d) Structural Adherence: Structure adherence evaluates how well the LLM conforms to the specified JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) format, ensuring correct field names, proper nesting, and consistent formatting. Each output was fed to an online JSON validator to determine whether it is correctly structured and ready for direct use or requires modifications. Each aspect was rated on a scale from 1 (poor performance) to 5 (excellent performance), which enabled a systematic comparison of the strengths and weaknesses of the LLMs.

Finally, the LLMs' performances were optimised with prompt engineering. The prompts were refined by incorporating domain-specific knowledge and structured output requirements. The models with optimised prompts were then reevaluated using the same criteria system, allowing for a performance comparison between basic and engineered prompts and the quantification of the impact of prompt optimisation on extraction quality.

IV. MODEL ANALYSIS

a) Evaluation of LLM Performance: The evaluation of the four chosen LLMs reveals distinct strengths and weaknesses across the key performance metrics: accuracy, depth, and hallucination rate. The average values with and without prompt optimization are shown in Fig. 1. In terms of accuracy, Claude 3.5 Sonnet slightly outperforms the other models, indicating that it consistently extracts key facts more reliably than the others. ChatGPT 4o follows closely behind, also demonstrating strong performance in identifying correct details. Llama 3.1 and Gemini 1.5 Flash exhibit slightly lower accuracy, suggesting they may occasionally miss or misinterpret important information. Both Claude and ChatGPT excel in the depth of extraction and capture comprehensive background information, technical details, and contextual nuances from the articles. By contrast, Gemini and Llama can extract essential information, but fail to provide the same level of depth and richness in their responses as the leading models. Finally, Gemini barely hallucinates, scoring 4.96 in hallucination rate. While Claude and Llama also achieve high scores, indicating that they are also very reliable in avoiding fabricated information, ChatGPT4-o has a slightly lower score and occasionally introduces incorrect details.

Fig. 1: Performance comparison between original and optimised prompts

b) Impact of Prompt Engineering: Following best practices of prompt engineering [18], a remodelled prompt included the instruction to output only valid JSON and not to hallucinate by limiting the results to information in the text. Additionally, it clearly defined the expected JSON structure. Results of the improved prompt showed improvements in all three key performance metrics, see Fig. 1. Accuracy improved slightly, though challenges in date extraction and fact-checking remained. Depth of extraction improved significantly, with some models providing more detailed context, though others continued to offer shallow responses. While reducing hallucinations was not the primary goal, most models showed better performance. These findings suggest that refined prompt design helped mitigate unnecessary information generation.

c) Structural Adherence: Conformity of LLMs to the JSON output structure unexpectedly showed great variability. Claude (5.00) was the only model to produce valid JSON consistently, while ChatGPT (4.65), Llama (4.56), and Gemini (4.38) sometimes included comments within JSON, leading to invalid outputs. This underscores the need for stricter prompting, explicitly instructing models to exclude comments and follow structured formatting.

Overall, Claude 3.5 Sonnet emerges as the top performer, with high marks in accuracy, structural adherence, and depth, while maintaining a low hallucination rate. ChatGPT 4o also performs well across the board, particularly in depth, though it exhibits a slightly higher tendency to hallucinate. Therefore, both models were chosen to be integrated into the data processing pipeline.

V. ARTIFACT GENERATION

This chapter details the development and implementation of the LLM-based IE system for SDC news as the main artifact. The goal was to create a seamless replacement for the existing rule-based system while significantly enhancing the platform's ability to extract and process information from SDC news articles.

a) Implementation of the LLM APIs: The implementation of Claude 3.5 Sonnet and GPT-4o follows a straightforward workflow: scraping SDC-relevant articles from the web or PDF-based newsletters [5] and saving them as JSON file [19], loading the articles.json file, sending individual articles to the respective LLM for processing, converting the returned JSON responses (which might be more than one per article if multiple cables are mentioned) into a Pandas DataFrame, and finally generating the dataset update vectors (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2: System architecture of the LLM-based IE pipeline.

b) *Multi-Model Support*: The implementation allows for model selection at runtime, either through command-line parameters or default configuration. The core IE logic remains constant, with only API-specific handling differing. This is achieved through two different functions for the actual API call, one for Anthropic and one for OpenAI. They both return output of the same structure, so the post-processing is executed by other, model-independent functions.

c) *Token Counting and Cost Management*: The LLM processing is sidelined with a monitoring unit to track performance indicators and costs. Each article is processed by embedding its text within XML tags and sending it to the API along with the system prompt and model configuration. This continues until all articles are processed, generating the final output file. To manage processing costs, a token counting function tracks both input and output tokens, as costs are based on the total tokens used. Different models have varying token limits, such as Claude 3.5 Sonnet (200,000 tokens) and GPT-4o (128,000 tokens). The implementation includes real-time cost estimation using current pricing data, though actual costs may vary due to provider optimizations.

VI. EVALUATION AND POST-TESTS

The evaluation covers two main areas: performance analysis of the implemented solution and a comparison with a rule-based approach.

a) *Performance Analysis*: The performance analysis revealed distinct variations in processing speed and cost efficiency across different extraction approaches. The rule-based approach, serving as our baseline, demonstrated consistent processing speeds of 17 seconds for 20 articles. When evaluating LLM-based solutions, including the newly integrated Claude 3.5 Haiku model, both Claude variants showed comparable processing patterns, though Haiku exhibited slightly longer processing times for large datasets while offering significant cost advantages - processing 176 articles cost \$0.4704 with Haiku versus \$1.395 with Sonnet.

OpenAI's models displayed notable performance characteristics: GPT-4o performed well with small datasets but experienced slower processing times with larger ones due to API rate limitations. In contrast, GPT-4o-mini proved more efficient, processing the complete dataset in 5 minutes compared to GPT-4o's 11 minutes, while maintaining the lowest cost at \$0.0714 for 176 articles. The time complexity analysis showed linear scaling for the rule-based approach, while LLM processing exhibited a flattened curve due to their ability to skip articles lacking relevant SDC information, unlike the rule-based system which processes all articles uniformly.

b) *Comparative Evaluation*: The comparison used three standard metrics: precision (the proportion of correctly extracted information among all extractions), recall (the proportion of relevant information successfully extracted) and the F1 score (the harmonic mean of precision and recall, providing a balanced measure of precision) which are standard metrics in statistical LLM analysis. These metrics were calculated by comparing the extracted data with a manually annotated

ground truth dataset, created in a previous project by Beuck, Ebbinghaus, Lukas, *et al.* [19]. The results, as presented in Table II, demonstrate a substantial performance gap between the LLM-based and rule-based approaches. Claude 3.5 Sonnet achieved the highest overall F1 score of 0.268, followed by GPT-4o (0.233) and GPT-4o mini (0.208), while the rule-based system significantly underperformed with an F1 score of 0.016. This order-of-magnitude difference highlights the limitations of rigid pattern matching and predefined rules in handling the complexity and variability of natural language in news articles. At the same time, even those F1 scores are relatively low and point at the need for further refinement of the extraction systems.

TABLE II: Performance comparison of IE approaches

Model	Precision	Recall	F1 Score	Processing Time
Claude 3.5 Sonnet	0.230	0.329	0.268	2m 47s
GPT-4o	0.228	0.263	0.233	1m 40s
GPT-4o mini	0.176	0.266	0.208	1m 01s
Rule-based	0.018	0.016	0.016	20s

Analysis of specific extraction categories, as shown in Table III, reveals distinct patterns in performance across different types of IE tasks. All LLM variants demonstrated the strongest performance in identifying cable deployment status and operational status information, such as cable breaks. This success can be attributed to the explicit and standardised way in which these events are typically reported in news articles. The rule-based system struggled significantly with these tasks, achieving negligible F1 scores in the two categories it was optimized for detection.

TABLE III: Comparison of F1 scores across key extraction categories

Category	Claude 3.5	GPT-4o	GPT-4o mini	Rule-based
pot_new_cable	0.540	0.561	0.459	0.100
broken	0.536	0.468	0.400	N/A
planned	0.542	0.478	0.340	N/A
out_of_service	0.302	0.200	0.196	0.048

The detection of cable breaks, a critical aspect of SDC monitoring, demonstrates well the advantages of LLM-based approaches. As shown in Table IV, Claude 3.5 Sonnet achieved the highest performance in break detection. GPT-4o showed similar precision but lower recall, while the rule-based system did not correctly identify any cable breaks, producing only false positives and missing all actual events. This performance variation reveals the LLMs' ability to understand context and variations in how cable breaks are described in news articles.

The performance advantage of LLMs comes with a trade-off in processing time. While the rule-based system completed the extraction task for the test data set of 20 articles in just 20 seconds, the LLM approaches required significantly more time. Claude 3.5 Sonnet took 2 minutes and 47 seconds, GPT-4o needed 1 minute and 40 seconds, and GPT-4o mini took 1 minute and 1 second. However, given the substantial improvement in extraction accuracy, this time investment appears justified for applications where precision is paramount. Still, even advanced LLMs face challenges when dealing with highly specific technical details, although they outperformed rule-based methods in this evaluation.

Fig. 3: Performance comparison of different extraction approaches

TABLE IV: Detailed analysis of cable break detection performance. True Positives (TP), False Positives (FP), False Negatives (FN).

Model	Precision	Recall	F1 Score	TP/FP/FN
Claude 3.5 Sonnet	0.469	0.625	0.536	15/17/9
GPT-4o	0.478	0.458	0.468	11/12/13
GPT-4o mini	0.370	0.435	0.400	10/17/13

VII. DISCUSSION

The analysis and the successful implementation of a data extractor demonstrate that LLMs can be effectively applied through a structured, multi-stage approach that leverages their natural language understanding capabilities while accounting for domain-specific requirements. In direct response to the RQ, this work demonstrates that LLMs can be effectively applied to extract and process SDC news data through (1) careful model selection based on empirical performance evaluation for the specific use case, (2) prompt optimization tailored to specific extraction tasks, and (3) robust implementation of structured data models and validation mechanisms.

The work revealed three critical success factors: balancing accuracy with efficiency in model selection, implementing robust error handling mechanisms, and maintaining a modular architecture adaptable to emerging models and requirements. It demonstrated that LLMs can effectively transform unstructured textual information from various sources into structured data, though their capabilities vary across information types. The significant performance improvements over rule-based approaches, combined with the system's inherent flexibility, establish LLMs as a viable solution for the technical domain IE. Despite limitations in processing highly specific technical details, the successful implementation establishes a framework adaptable to various technical domains requiring automated text processing. This approach provides a foundation for future applications where structured data must be extracted from unstructured text sources.

a) Limitations: The evaluation is based on a dataset of 27 articles, which may influence the generalizability of findings, particularly in assessing model performance patterns and comparative analyses. Similarly, the evaluation of the implementation, comparing the new LLM-based extractor with the

rule-based approach, relies on a relatively small ground truth, which may affect the robustness of the findings. Additionally, the rapid advancement of LLMs presents a challenge, as newer models could outperform those evaluated here, potentially altering the comparative results over time.

b) Future Research: Fine-tuning LLMs for SDC news analysis is a promising direction. While the current system relies on prompt engineering, fine-tuning could improve performance, especially for technical specifications and industry-specific terms, but it requires a well-annotated dataset of SDC news for optimal results. Another current limitation is the lack of advanced Event Coreference Resolution (ECR) mechanisms [20], as while the system successfully identifies individual events, it does not yet effectively track and correlate related events across multiple sources. Implementing ECR in future research could offer greater analytical value and improve event monitoring capabilities. Those interested to further advance this research are invited to contact the first author for access to the public parts of the code, project documentation, and prompts via franken@peasec.tu-darmstadt.de.

VIII. CONCLUSION

This paper investigated the application of LLMs for extracting and processing news data in the SDC network domain. The research addressed the automated monitoring and analysis of SDC events, demonstrating that LLMs can effectively replace rule-based approaches while providing substantially improved performance. Most notably, the research demonstrated that carefully prompted LLMs can achieve significantly higher accuracy in IE compared to rule-based methods. A key contribution of this work is the development of a modular, adaptable system architecture that enables the seamless integration of different LLM providers. The implementation demonstrated that LLMs can be used effectively for specialised technical domains while maintaining output reliability and consistency. The use of structured prompts and robust output validation mechanisms proved essential for achieving consistent performance across various IE tasks. The research highlights limitations in LLM applications for technical domains. While being effective in reading between the lines of natural language

news articles, the models struggled with specific details like costs and capacities. Here, a hybrid approach may be optimal. Additionally, analysis of processing times, token usage, and costs can inform future deployments. Though LLMs are slower than rule-based methods, their accuracy often justifies trade-offs, and emerging smaller models may soon reduce this gap.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research work was funded by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research and the Hessian Ministry of Science and Research, Arts and Culture within their joint support of the National Research Center for Applied Cybersecurity ATHENE as well as the LOEWE initiative (Hesse, Germany) within the emergenCITY centre. Funding code: LOEWE/1/12/519/03/05.001(0016)/72. The authors would like to thank Karen Beuck, Lydia Ebbinghaus, Thies Lukas, and Lennart Oestreich for their programming contributions to the rule-based data processing pipeline, as well as SubCableNews for the permission to analyse SDC-related articles from their database.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. Kavanagh, J. Franken, and J. Kulesza, "In Oceans and in Orbits: The Infrastructure Essential to the Public Core of the Internet," in *Protecting the Internet's Core*, D. W. Brouders and A. M. Sakumar, Eds., Cambridge, MA: MIT Press, forthcoming 2025.
- [2] C. Bueger and T. Liebetrau, "Protecting hidden infrastructure: The security politics of the global submarine data cable network," *Contemporary Security Policy*, vol. 42, no. 3, pp. 391–413, Jul. 3, 2021. DOI: 10.1080/13523260.2021.1907129.
- [3] C. Kavanagh, J. Franken, and W. He, "Achieving depth: Subsea telecommunications cables as critical infrastructure," United Nations Institute for Disarmament Research (UNIDIR), Geneva, Tech. Rep., 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://unidir.org/publication/achieving-depth-subsea-telecommunications-cables-as-critical-infrastructure/> (visited on 05/20/2025).
- [4] K. Clark and S. Humera, "Submarine Cable Almanac - Issue 50," Submarine Telecoms Forum, Inc., cc, 50, May 2024.
- [5] SubCableNews. "Subcablenews." (2025), [Online]. Available: <https://subcablenews.com/> (visited on 02/20/2025).
- [6] J. Franken and C. Reuter, "The Subsea Data Cable Security Map – Fusing Public Information for Enhanced Critical Maritime Infrastructure Security," in *Proceedings of the MARESEC 2024 / Transactions on Maritime Science*, Bremerhaven, Germany, Nov. 2024. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14216269.
- [7] D. Xu, W. Chen, W. Peng, *et al.*, "Large language models for generative information extraction: A survey," *Frontiers of Computer Science*, vol. 18, no. 6, p. 186 357, Dec. 2024, ISSN: 2095-2228, 2095-2236. DOI: 10.1007/s11704-024-40555-y.
- [8] J. Evans, S. Sadruddin, and J. D'Souza, "Astro-NER – Astronomy Named Entity Recognition: Is GPT a Good Domain Expert Annotator?" arXiv: 2405.02602 [cs, math]. (May 4, 2024), [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2405.02602> (visited on 06/19/2024), pre-published.
- [9] S. Bogdanov, A. Constantin, T. Bernard, B. Crabbé, and E. Bernard. "NuNER: Entity Recognition Encoder Pre-training via LLM-Annotated Data." arXiv: 2402.15343 [cs]. (Feb. 23, 2024), [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2402.15343> (visited on 06/19/2024), pre-published.
- [10] S. Wang, X. Sun, X. Li, *et al.* "GPT-NER: Named Entity Recognition via Large Language Models." arXiv: 2304.10428 [cs]. (Oct. 7, 2023), [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2304.10428> (visited on 06/19/2024), pre-published.
- [11] Z. Zhang, Y. Zhao, H. Gao, and M. Hu, "LinkNER: Linking Local Named Entity Recognition Models to Large Language Models using Uncertainty," in *Proceedings of the ACM Web Conference 2024*, Singapore Singapore: ACM, May 13, 2024, pp. 4047–4058. DOI: 10.1145/3589334.3645414.
- [12] Z. Wan, F. Cheng, Z. Mao, *et al.*, "GPT-RE: In-context Learning for Relation Extraction using Large Language Models," in *Proceedings of the 2023 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing*, Singapore: Association for Computational Linguistics, 2023, pp. 3534–3547. DOI: 10.18653/v1/2023.emnlp-main.214.
- [13] P.-L. Huguet Cabot and R. Navigli, "REBEL: Relation Extraction By End-to-end Language generation," in *Findings of the Association for Computational Linguistics: EMNLP 2021*, M.-F. Moens, X. Huang, L. Specia, and S. W. Yih, Eds., Punta Cana, Dominican Republic: Association for Computational Linguistics, Nov. 2021, pp. 2370–2381. DOI: 10.18653/v1/2021.findings-emnlp.204.
- [14] X. Xu, Y. Zhu, X. Wang, and N. Zhang, "How to unleash the power of large language models for few-shot relation extraction?" In *Proceedings of the Fourth Workshop on Simple and Efficient Natural Language Processing (SustaiNLP)*, 2023, pp. 190–200.
- [15] M. Josifoski, N. De Cao, M. Peyrard, F. Petroni, and R. West, "GenIE: Generative Information Extraction," in *Proceedings of the 2022 Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Human Language Technologies*, Seattle, United States: Association for Computational Linguistics, 2022, pp. 4626–4643. DOI: 10.18653/v1/2022.naacl-main.342.
- [16] N. Nakshatri, S. Liu, S. Chen, D. Roth, D. Goldwasser, and D. Hopkins, "Using LLM for Improving Key Event Discovery: Temporal-Guided News Stream Clustering with Event Summaries," in *Findings of the Association for Computational Linguistics: EMNLP 2023*, H. Bouamor, J. Pino, and K. Bali, Eds., Singapore: Association for Computational Linguistics, Dec. 2023, pp. 4162–4173. DOI: 10.18653/v1/2023.findings-emnlp.274.
- [17] TeleGeography. "Submarine Cable Map." (Jun. 13, 2024), [Online]. Available: <https://www.submarinecablemap.com/> (visited on 06/14/2024).
- [18] A. Subramanian. "An Introduction to Prompting for LLMs," Medium. (Feb. 22, 2024), [Online]. Available: <https://towardsdatascience.com/an-introduction-to-prompting-for-llms-61d36a6c2048> (visited on 10/31/2024).
- [19] K. Beuck, L. Ebbinghaus, T. Lukas, and L. Oestreich, *Submarine Data Cable Security Dashboard - Web Scraping*, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://gitlab.dev.peasec.de/praktikum/24-ss-jf2-sdcs-web-scraping> (visited on 10/07/2024).
- [20] J. Lu and V. Ng, "Event Coreference Resolution: A Survey of Two Decades of Research," in *Proceedings of the Twenty-Seventh International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, Stockholm, Sweden: International Joint Conferences on Artificial Intelligence Organization, Jul. 2018, pp. 5479–5486. DOI: 10.24963/ijcai.2018/773.